

Solvent Extraction of Gallium from Malonic Acid with Amberlite LA-2

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Gallium was quantitatively extracted with 0.08 M Amberlite LA-2 in xylene at pH 3.0 from 0.01 M malonic acid and stripped from the organic phase with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid and then determined spectrophotometrically at 510 nm with PAR. It was separated from large number of elements with either selective extraction or stripping. The most interesting separation was from aluminium, indium and thallium.

SOLVENT extraction separation of gallium was generally carried out with solvating solvents from halo acids, but no attempt was made for its extraction with high molecular weight amines from the organic acid solutions. Gallium was extracted with high molecular weight amines from hydrochloric¹⁻⁴, hydrobromic⁵⁻⁷ and hydroiodic⁸ acids and was separated from elements, like aluminium, indium and thallium. All such extractions were carried out at 4-6 M acid concentration with Amberlite LA-1, LA-2; trioctylamine or triisooctylamine extraction, the optimum conditions for the quantitative extraction are evaluated and several interesting separations have been carried out.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: A ECIL 822 digital pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes, a ECIL GS 866C spectrophotometer with matched 10 mm Corex glass cells, and a Toshniwal wrist-action flask shaker were used.

A stock solution of gallium was prepared by dissolving 0.50 g metal (Johnson Mathey) in 20 ml concentrated nitric acid and evaporated to dryness, and then extracting the residue with 250 ml of distilled water containing 2.5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised complexometrically with EDTA using galloxyanine as indicator¹⁰. It contained 2 mg ml⁻¹ of gallium. The solution containing 20 µg ml⁻¹ gallium was prepared by dilution.

Amberlite LA-1, Amberlite LA-2, Primene JM-T (Rohm and Haas, U.S.A.); Aliquat 336 S (General Mills, England); TOA and TIOA (Riedel Haen, Germany) were used without further purification. These exchangers were converted into malonate form by the procedure described earlier¹¹. 4-(2-Pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR) and malonic acid were of Riedel Haen and Co., Germany. A 0.1% aqueous solution of PAR was used. Buffer solution of pH 4.0 was prepared by mixing 1 M acetic acid (284 ml)

with 1 M sodium hydroxide (50 ml) and making the total volume to 500 ml with distilled water.

General procedure: To an aliquot containing gallium (20 µg), 0.02 M malonic acid (5 ml) was added. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to 3.0 with dilute NaOH or malonic acid. The final volume of solution was made to 10 ml. It was transferred to a separatory funnel and shaken with 4% Amberlite LA-2 (10 ml) in xylene for 5 min on wrist-action flask shaker. The aqueous phase was discarded and organic phase was shaken again with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid (10 ml) to strip off gallium. The aqueous layer was withdrawn, evaporated almost to dryness and treated with water (5 ml). Buffer solution (5 ml) of pH 4.0 was added followed by 0.1% aqueous PAR solution (2 ml). The volume was made to 25 ml with distilled water and absorbance was measured on a spectrophotometer at 510 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of gallium was computed from the calibration curve¹².

Results and Discussion

Extraction as a function of pH: The pH of extraction was varied between 1.0 to 8.0. Fig. 1 shows the results for 4% solution of amines in xylene. The optimum pH for quantitative extraction was 2.5 to 4.0 with Amberlite LA-2, 3.0 to 4.0 with Primene JM-T, and 4.0 to 5.0 with Aliquot 336 S. The extraction was incomplete (between 70 to 25%) with Amberlite LA-1, trioctylamine and triisooctylamine. Therefore, Amberlite LA-2 was selected for further study.

Effect of various diluents: The extraction of gallium was carried out with Amberlite LA-2 in different diluents (Table 1). The phase volume ratio was kept at unity to avoid emulsion. Benzene and xylene were found to be most efficient diluents. Toluene, hexane and cyclohexane were equally effective but carbon tetrachloride and chloroform showed somewhat low extraction while hexanone

Fig. 1. Extraction of Ga from malonic acid solution by various 4% amine solutions in xylene: (●) Amberlite LA-2, (○) Primene JM-T, (△) Aliquat 336 S, (□) Amberlite LA-1, (○) TOA and (▲) TIOA.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIOUS DILUENTS

Ga = 20 μ g, pH = 3.0, Amberlite LA-2 = 8×10^{-3} M

Diluent	Dielectric constant	Extraction %
Benzene	2.28	100.0
Toluene	2.38	99.2
Xylene	2.30	100.0
Carbon tetrachloride	2.24	82.4
Chloroform	4.80	89.8
Hexane	1.89	98.2
Cyclohexane	2.05	98.2
Methyl isobutyl ketone	13.10	22.2

proved to be a poor diluent. For all practical purposes, xylene was preferred as the diluent.

Effect of Amberlite LA-2 concentration : Keeping malonic acid concentration constant, gallium was extracted with varying concentration of Amberlite

LA-2 in xylene (Table 2). It was observed that extraction commenced at 1×10^{-3} M but was quantitative from 7×10^{-3} M concentration of Amberlite LA-2. Hence, 8×10^{-3} M of Amberlite LA-2 was selected as the optimum concentration for the quantitative extraction of gallium.

Effect of malonic acid concentration : The concentration of malonic acid was varied from 2×10^{-4} to 10×10^{-4} M with all other factors kept constant (Table 3). The extraction commenced with 2×10^{-4} M

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF AMBERLITE LA-2 CONCENTRATION

Ga = 20 μ g, pH = 3.0, xylene as diluent

Amberlite LA-2 1×10^{-3} M	Extraction (E) %	Distribution ratio (D)
1.0	9.2	0.10
1.5	27.8	0.39
2.0	49.1	0.96
2.5	65.7	1.90
3.0	76.9	3.33
3.5	84.3	5.37
4.0	89.8	8.80
4.5	93.5	14.40
5.0	95.4	20.73
6.0	99.1	110.00
7.0	100.0	∞
8.0	100.0	∞

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF MALONIC ACID CONCENTRATION

Ga = 20 μ g, pH = 3.0, Amberlite LA-2 in xylene = 8×10^{-3} M

Malonic acid 1×10^{-4} M	Extraction (E) %	Distribution ratio (D)
2.0	25.0	0.33
2.5	38.9	0.64
3.0	53.7	1.16
3.5	65.7	1.90
4.0	74.0	2.85
4.5	80.5	4.12
5.0	85.2	5.76
6.0	91.7	11.05
7.0	94.5	17.13
8.0	98.1	51.63
9.0	100.0	∞
10.0	100.0	∞

malonic acid, but it was quantitative at concentration greater than 9×10^{-4} M. Although the complexation was complete with 10×10^{-4} M malonic acid, for all practical purposes 10×10^{-3} M was used to ensure complete extraction.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF BACK-STRIPPING AGENTS

Stripping agent (M)	Extraction %							
	0.1	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	6.0	8.0
HCl	16.7	100.0	100.0	55.6	29.6	20.4	<2.0	<2.0
HBr	14.8	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	64.8	<4.0	—
HI	—	100.0	100.0	63.0	38.9	22.2	<5.0	—
H ₂ SO ₄	29.6	24.0	40.7	42.6	—	—	—	—
HNO ₃	83.3	100.0	100.0	100.0	98.1	95.4	92.6	92.6
Na ₂ CO ₃	<5.0	29.6	98.9	—	—	—	—	—
NaOH	<5.0	25.9	31.5	42.6	—	—	—	—
NH ₄ OH	9.3	50.0	88.9	64.8	—	—	—	—

Effect of stripping agents: Various mineral acids and bases were used as stripping agents in the concentration range of 0.1 to 8 M (Table 4). The stripping was found to be complete with 0.5 M of hydrochloric, hydrobromic, hydroiodic or nitric acid. With alkali hydroxide, quantitative stripping was not possible. Although it was possible to strip gallium with 0.5 to 3 M of either hydrobromic or nitric acid, hydrochloric acid (0.5 to 1 M) was preferred on account of the ease of evaporation prior to quantitative determination of gallium with PAR¹².

Period of equilibration: The period of extraction as well as stripping was varied from 1 to 30 min. The extraction was quantitative in 5 min period of equilibration, whereas stripping operation was complete in 2 min. Therefore, 5 min period of shaking was employed during extraction and stripping work.

Nature of species extracted: This is thought to be an ion-pair complex with the possible composition as (R₃NH₃)₃Ga(malonate)₃. This formulation was supported by graphical evidence. The slopes of plots of log D vs log [amine] at fixed malonic acid concentration, and log D vs log [malonic acid] at fixed amine concentration, were 3.05 and 3.11, respectively. This confirmed the existence of trisolvated species.

Separation of gallium from other elements: The effect of diverse ions was examined as in the previous work¹¹. The tolerance limit was set as usual. The results are shown in Table 5. Alkali, alkaline earths, Tl^I, Fe^{II}, Ag, As^{III}, Y and all lanthanides (except La, Pr, Nd and Ce^{III}) were incapable of forming malonate complexes and were not extracted, and thus they were separated from gallium.

Zn, Cd, Ni, Co, Al, Pb, Mn, La, Pr and Nd formed weak complexes with malonic acid. Thus after their extraction along with gallium, these complexes were dissociated by scrubbing the organic phase with water, leaving behind gallium in the organic phase. Then gallium was stripped with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid.

Gallium was separated from Bi, Sb, Tl^{III}, Hg^{II} and Pt^{IV} first by extraction of all the elements as malonate complexes, followed by stripping off only gallium with 1 M hydrochloric acid into the aqueous phase. Thus, other elements remaining behind in the organic phase as anionic chloro complexes were in turn stripped with 0.5 M sodium hydroxide. Sc, Ti^{IV}, V^{IV}, Zr^{IV} and Ce^{III} were extracted along with gallium as stable anionic complexes. They were first back-stripped with 6 M hydrochloric acid. Gallium was then stripped with 0.5 M of either hydrochloric or nitric acid. Such separations were feasible as gallium formed strong chloro complex at 6 M acid concentration and remained in the organic phase¹⁻⁴.

The separation of gallium from U^{VI}, Th and In was carried out in nitrate media. After extraction of gallium with these elements from malonate media, it was stripped first with 4 M nitric acid leaving behind the other elements in the organic phase as

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Ga=20 μg, pH=3.0, Amberlite LA-2=8 × 10⁻² M

Foreign ion	Added as	Tolerance limit μg
Li	Li ₂ SO ₄ ·H ₂ O	4000
Na	NaCl	6000
K	KCl	6000
Rb	RbCl	1000
Cs	CsCl	1200
Be ^{II}	Be(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	2000
Mg ^{II}	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1600
Ca ^{II}	CaCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	2000
Sr ^{II}	Sr(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1800
Ba ^{II}	Ba(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	2000
Tl ^I	Tl ₂ SO ₄	400
Fe ^{II}	FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	200
Ag ^I	AgNO ₃	350
As ^{III}	AsCl ₃	300
Y ^{III}	Y(NO ₃) ₃	600
La ^{III}	La(NO ₃) ₃	200
Pr ^{III}	Pr(NO ₃) ₃	220
Nd ^{III}	Nd(NO ₃) ₃	300
Sm ^{III}	Sm(NO ₃) ₃	200
Gd ^{III}	Gd(NO ₃) ₃	280
Dy ^{III}	Dy(NO ₃) ₃	300
Zn ^{II}	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	200
Cd ^{II}	3Cd(NO ₃) ₂ ·8H ₂ O	320
Ni ^{II}	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	300
Co ^{II}	Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	200
Cr ^{III}	Cr(NO ₃) ₃ ·9H ₂ O	180
Al ^{III}	Al(NO ₃) ₃ ·9H ₂ O	400
Pb ^{II}	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	250
Mn ^{II}	MnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	150
Pt ^{IV}	H ₂ PtCl ₆ ·xH ₂ O	200
Au ^{III}	AuCl ₃	200
Bi ^{III}	Bi(NO ₃) ₃ ·5H ₂ O	200
Sb ^{III}	SbCl ₃ ·8H ₂ O	250
Tl ^{III}	TlCl ₃	260
Hg ^{II}	HgCl ₂	300
Sc ^{III}	Sc(NO ₃) ₃	350
Ti ^{IV}	Ti(SO ₄) ₂	375
V ^{IV}	VO ₂ ·3H ₂ O	100
Zr ^{IV}	Zr(NO ₃) ₄ ·5H ₂ O	200
Ce ^{III}	Ce(NO ₃) ₃	140
In ^{III}	In ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ ·5H ₂ O	275
Th ^{IV}	Th(NO ₃) ₄ ·4H ₂ O	300
U ^{VI}	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	150
SeO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ SeO ₃	350
SiO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ SiO ₃	375
B ₄ O ₇ ²⁻	Na ₂ B ₄ O ₇	250
Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ⁴⁻	(NH ₄) ₂ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	150
WO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ WO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	250

nitrate complexes. Then they were stripped with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid. Gallium was separated from oxyanions, such as selenite, silicate, borate,

molybdate and tungstate by selective stripping. Thus, gallium was stripped first with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid followed by stripping of oxyanions with 0.5 M sodium hydroxide.

Separation of Ga from Al, In and Tl : It was possible to separate these ions by the process of selective stripping. First, all these elements were extracted with 4% Amberlite LA-2 in xylene from 0.01 M malonic acid at pH 3.0. Since aluminium formed weak anionic malonato complex, it was washed into the aqueous phase with water and thus separated from other ions. A 2 M hydrobromic acid was found to be effective stripping agent for gallium⁵⁻⁷. Hence, it was stripped from the organic phase with 2 M hydrobromic acid (10 ml). A 0.5 M hydrochloric acid proved to be efficient stripping agent for indium¹². So it was stripped with 0.5 M hydrochloric acid (10 ml). Thallium remained in the organic phase as chloro complex. At pH~10, 0.01 M EDTA was found to be best stripping agent for thallium(III)¹⁴ (Table 6). Hence, thallium was quantitatively re-extracted with 0.01 M EDTA (10 ml) buffered at pH~10. In such a separation, thallium(I)

did not interfere as it formed on anionic complex with malonic acid.

The proposed method is rapid, simple and selective and is applicable at microgram concentration. Concentration as low as 0.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of gallium can be quantitatively determined. The separation of gallium from aluminium, indium and thallium is important as they are usually associated with it. From ten runs with 20 μg of gallium, the average recovery was $99.9 \pm 1\%$ and relative standard deviation 1%.

References

1. A. R. SRELMER-OLSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1966, **20**, 1621.
2. R. PRIBIL and V. VESELY, *Talanta*, 1970, **17**, 801.
3. G. NAKAGAWA, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1960, **81**, 1533.
4. M. L. GOOD, S. C. SRIVASTAVA and F. F. HOLLAND, Jr., *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 534.
5. T. SUZUKI and T. SOTOBAYASHI, *Jpn. Analyst*, 1963, **12**, 910.
6. SH. A. SHERIFF, A. S. ABDEL-GAWAD and A. M. EL-WAKIL, *Talanta*, 1970, **17**, 137.
7. T. SUZUKI, *Jpn. Analyst*, 1966, **15**, 662.
8. T. SUZUKI and T. SOTOBAYASHI, *Jpn. Analyst*, 1965, **14**, 420.
9. N. B. MIKHREEV, G. I. ELFIMOVA, L. M. MIKHREVA and I. A. RUMER, *Ser. Khim.*, 1970, **11**, 742 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1971, **21**, 2457).
10. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid", Van Nostrand, London, 1958, p. 178.
11. M. B. DALVI and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Talanta*, 1978, **25**, 599.
12. F. D. SNELL, "Photometric and Fluorometric Methods of Analysis", John Wiley, 1978, Part I p. 513.
13. R. BAGHUNADHA RAO and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, communicated.
14. T. SUZUKI and T. SOTOBAYASHI, *Jpn. Analyst*, 1965, **14**, 414.

TABLE 6—SEPARATION OF Ga FROM Al, In AND Tl

pH=8.0 Amberlite LA-2= 8×10^{-3} M Malonic acid= 1×10^{-3} M				
Ion	Taken μg	Found μg	Recovery %	Eluant
Al	350.6	351.0	100.11	Water
Ga	20.0	20.0	103.0	2 M HBr
In	255.0	252.6	99.06	0.5 M HCl
Tl	250.8	250.0	99.68	0.01 M EDTA